

Dual-Channel OOK (D-COOK) Modulation for UAV-Assisted Mixed THz/VLC Systems

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Abstract—This paper investigates a dual-hop UAV-assisted communications system that integrates Terahertz (THz) and Visible Light Communication (VLC) over a decode-and-forward (DF) relay that bridges the THz and VLC segments. The VLC channel is modelled to account for additive background noise and deterministic fading, while the THz link is subject to path loss, absorption loss, and pointing errors. A comparative analysis with Free Space Optics (FSO)-VLC and Radio Frequency (RF)-VLC systems highlights the superior performance of the THz-VLC system, especially at high signal-to-noise ratios (SNR), in terms of BER and outage probability. Furthermore, a novel modulation technique is proposed that enables increased data rates. Performance evaluation of the proposed modulation scheme further validates the effectiveness of the system.

Index Terms—UAV, THz, VLC, Modulation, DF Relay

I. INTRODUCTION

As the demand for wireless connectivity continues to escalate, the limitations of the radio frequency (RF) spectrum have become increasingly pronounced. With the advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) and the proliferation of interconnected devices, traditional RF-based communication systems are struggling to cope with the increasing demands of data. The RF spectrum is not only congested but also subject to interference, leading to suboptimal performance in dense environments. This situation is exacerbated by the growing need for higher data rates, lower latency, and more reliable connections, especially in scenarios that require massive device connectivity and high-throughput applications [1]. To address these challenges, researchers are exploring alternative communication technologies that can alleviate the pressure on

the RF spectrum. VLC has emerged as a promising candidate, operating within the visible light spectrum (400–700 nm), which is largely untapped for data transmission. VLC offers several technical advantages over RF, including significantly higher available bandwidth, inherent security through line-of-sight communication, and minimal electromagnetic interference. Additionally, VLC systems can be seamlessly integrated with existing Light Emitting Diode (LED) lighting infrastructure, enabling dual-purpose functionality that supports both illumination and high-speed data transmission.

Despite several advantages, VLC's widespread adoption is impeded by challenges such as significant signal degradation from sunlight interference in outdoor settings. To mitigate these issues, hybrid VLC systems have been proposed, which utilize VLC indoors and conventional communication technologies outdoors, supported by cooperative relay architectures. This strategy aims to leverage the strengths of the VLC while addressing some of its practical limitations [2].

Several studies have explored hybrid RF/VLC systems [3]–[5], where RF is used for outdoor communication and VLC for indoor connectivity. This configuration successfully addresses the challenges faced by VLC in outdoor environments. However, a significant drawback of this approach is that the performance of the indoor VLC link is constrained by the lower data rate of the RF link, creating a bottleneck. Although this hybrid system benefits from the robustness of RF outdoors and the high data rates of VLC indoors, the overall performance is limited by the weaker RF link, leading to a trade-off between resolving outdoor issues and managing data rate limitations. One proposed solution to this bottleneck is to use a higher-bandwidth communication technology than RF. Several studies have investigated the use of FSO instead of RF for outdoor communication in hybrid VLC systems [6]–[8]. Although FSO offers higher bandwidth, it is severely affected by atmospheric conditions such as fog, smog, and rain, which significantly degrade system performance. To address the limitations of both RF

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and FSO as backhaul links, our previous work [9] introduced Terahertz (THz) communication as a promising alternative for outdoor links in hybrid Visible Light Communication (VLC) systems. Operating within the 0.1 to 10 THz frequency range, THz communication offers substantial advantages, including extensive bandwidth, low latency, and high directional gain.

This paper extends the work of [9] by introducing a dual-hop UAV-assisted THz-VLC system. Unlike the Binary Phase-shift Keying (BPSK) and On-Off Keying (OOK) modulations used in [9], our system uses Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) for THz links and a novel Dual-Channel OOK (D-COOK) modulation scheme for the indoor VLC link. This proposed modulation scheme uses RGB LEDs to transmit 2 bits per symbol by combining two OOK signals. This new scheme aims to improve the efficiency and reliability of data transmission, addressing the limitations of conventional modulation techniques used in hybrid VLC systems [3]–[9]. Performance is assessed through simulations focusing on BER, channel capacity, and outage probability.

However from a practical standpoint, implementing THz-VLC hybrid systems involves addressing several challenges such as path loss, pointing errors, and environmental and weather conditions. Effective mitigation strategies, including advanced stabilization mechanisms, adaptive beam steering, efficient power management, and robust encryption, are essential for the successful deployment and operation of these systems in real-world scenarios.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model in Fig. 1 consists of a stationary camera-equipped UAV that transmits surveillance video through THz communication to a DF relay node. The relay decodes the THz signal and re-encodes it using VLC for final transmission inside the building. The THz link uses QAM, while the VLC link uses D-COOK, which combines two OOK streams with RGB LEDs to transmit two bits per symbol. This scheme is designed to boost data rates and reliability by minimizing inter-symbol interference (ISI) through color-based filtering.

The system-level equations are given below:

$$Y_{sr} = \sqrt{P_s} H_{THz} x + n_{SR}, \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{rd} = \sqrt{P_r} H_{VLC} \tilde{x} + n_{RD}, \quad (2)$$

where P_s is the source power, P_r is the relay power, H_{THz} is the THz channel, H_{VLC} is the VLC channel, x is the information signal, \tilde{x} is the signal encoded by the relay, and n_{SR} and n_{RD} are the noise from source to relay and relay to destination, respectively.

A. THz Channel Model

The THz channel gain is expressed as $H_{THz} = h_p h_a h_m$, where h_p , h_a and h_m are the free-space path loss, the molecular absorption loss and the misalignment fading effect, respectively.

Fig. 1. A stationary UAV transmits surveillance video via THz using 4-QAM to a DF relay, which forwards the re-encoded signal indoors using VLC using D-COOK, leveraging RGB LEDs to transmit 2 bits per symbol.

The LOS free space path loss can be modelled using the Friss equation [9] as, $h_p = \frac{c\sqrt{G_{TX}G_{RX}}}{4\pi df}$, where d is the distance between the transmitter and the receiver, f is the carrier frequency and G_{TX} and G_{RX} are the gain of the transmitter and receiver antenna, respectively.

The molecular absorption loss refers to the attenuation of THz waves due to the absorption of certain molecules in the transmission window. Molecules in the atmosphere, such as O_2 and $H_2O_{(g)}$, absorb a proportion of the energy emitted by the THz signals. This divides the THz frequency into several transmission windows. This phenomenon can be modelled as, $h_a = e^{-\frac{1}{2}k_a(f)d}$, where the absorption coefficient, $k_a(f)$, is the area per unit volume that medium molecules absorb energy from electromagnetic signals [9].

THz transceivers with directive antenna systems are highly vulnerable to UAV sway and environmental factors, which can cause misaligned antenna beams, resulting in pointing errors. The PDF of the misalignment fading effect is given as [9],

$$f h_m(x) = \frac{\zeta^2}{A_0^{\zeta^2}} x^{\zeta^2-1}, 0 \leq x \leq A_0 \quad (3)$$

where A_0 is the fraction of the power collected by the receiver and ζ is the ratio between the equivalent beam width and the standard deviation of the pointing error at the receiver.

B. VLC Channel Model

$$H_{VLC} = \begin{cases} \frac{A_{pd} L_0(\theta)}{D^2} \cos(\psi) T_s(\psi) g_s(\psi), & 0 < \psi < \psi_c \\ 0, & \psi > \psi_c, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In this study, it is assumed that the line-of-sight (LOS) path serves as the sole communication channel between the Photodiode (PD) and the LED. The gain of the VLC channel is expressed as in equation (4).

where A_{pd} is the photodiode area, L_0 is the LED radiation distribution function, D is the distance between the transmitter and the receiver, $T_s(\psi)$ is the filter gain, $g_s(\psi)$ is the

concentrator gain, and ψ is the Field of View (FoV) of the photodiode.

The radiation distribution function considering the number of radiation patterns m and the radiation angle of the LED θ can be expressed as $L_0(\theta) = \frac{m+1}{2\pi} \cos^m(\theta)$.

Conventional RF-based modulation schemes are not directly applicable to VLC systems. To address this limitation, a new modulation scheme based on OOK and CSK is proposed.

1) *D-COOK Modulation Scheme*: Fig. 2 illustrates the block diagram of the modulator and demodulator for this model. In the modulator section, the data stream is initially divided into two segments by considering the odd and even bits, similar to Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK). Subsequently, the odd bits are modulated using OOK with the red light of the RGB LED, while the even bits are modulated using OOK with the green light of the RGB LED. This approach combines two OOK signals to enhance the bits transmitted per symbol compared to conventional OOK.

One of the critical challenges with this approach is maintaining synchronization between RGB LEDs, which is essential to ensure that each color channel transmits the intended data without overlap or delay. Any desynchronization can cause timing mismatches between the red, green, and blue channels, leading to a significant degradation in signal quality. To mitigate this, precise control mechanisms such as clock-based hardware synchronization could be employed. These solutions help align the pulse trains from each channel and maintain consistency throughout the transmission.

Fig. 2. The block diagram of the modulator and demodulator of the proposed D-COOK scheme.

The modulated signal, $\hat{x} = x_1 + x_2$, where x_1 represents the modulated bits through red light and x_2 represents the modulated bits through green light, can be expressed as follow

$$x_1 = b_o g(t - iT_s), \quad (5)$$

$$x_2 = b_e g(t - iT_s), \quad (6)$$

where $g(t)$ is the rectangle pulse shape, and b_o and b_e are the odd and even bits, respectively.

In the demodulator section depicted in Fig. 2, the resultant light beam \hat{x} appears yellow due to the combination of red and green. However, two PDs at the receiver end incorporate red and green filters to decode the intended bits, thereby avoiding inter-symbol interference. However, imperfections in the spectral separation of RGB LEDs may result in some overlap between the channels. This overlap can cause ISI, which reduces the efficiency and reliability of data transmission. Optical filters with sharper cutoffs can help mitigate this, but in more advanced systems, adaptive filtering techniques or machine learning-based dynamic error correction can be applied to cancel out inter-channel interference and improve overall system performance.

The D-COOK modulation scheme utilizes RGB LEDs to simultaneously transmit two OOK signals in VLC systems. This is achieved by color-based separation to enhance data rates. Unlike Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM), which employs wavelength division in fiber-optic communication, D-COOK operates wirelessly in VLC by modulating distinct data streams over different visible-light colors. While D-COOK's use of RGB-based separation may resemble WDM, it fundamentally differs in both approach and application. Specifically, WDM is a multiplexing technique designed for optical fiber networks, where multiple data streams are transmitted over distinct wavelengths, whereas D-COOK exploits the visible spectrum for wireless communication by using the RGB channels of LEDs.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The THz-VLC link studied in this paper utilizes the new modulation scheme proposed in Sections II-B1. Since D-COOK modulation at the relay-destination link utilize a two Tx and two Rx setup, the system-level equation (2) should be modified. However, since no modification is made to the THz section, equation (1) can remain the same. If P_s is the source power and σ_{SR} is the noise power corresponding to n_{SR} , then the SNR for Y_{SR} can be expressed as $\gamma_1 = \frac{P_s |H_{THz}|^2}{\sigma_{SR}^2}$.

Now, considering the D-COOK modulation scheme, the modified system-level equations for the relay destination can be expressed as follows:

$$\hat{Y}_1 = \sqrt{P_r} H_{VLC} x_1 + n_{RD1}, \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{Y}_2 = \sqrt{P_r} H_{VLC} x_2 + n_{RD2}, \quad (8)$$

where \hat{Y}_1 and \hat{Y}_2 are the signals received in PD 1 and PD 2 respectively.

The SNRs for \hat{Y}_1 and \hat{Y}_2 are expressed as follows: $\gamma_2 = \frac{P_r |H_{VLC}|^2}{\sigma_1^2}$ and $\gamma_3 = \frac{P_r |H_{VLC}|^2}{\sigma_2^2}$, where σ_1 and σ_2 represent the noise powers corresponding to n_{RD1} and n_{RD2} , respectively.

In the context of the system model, an outage occurs when the SNR of the THz link or the VLC link falls below γ_{th} , a predefined threshold.

$$P(\gamma_1 < \gamma_{th}) = P\left(|H_{THz}|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th}}{P_s} \sigma_{SR}^2\right). \quad (9)$$

$$P(\gamma_2 < \gamma_{th}) = P\left(|H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th}}{P_r} \sigma_1^2\right), \quad (10)$$

$$P(\gamma_3 < \gamma_{th}) = P\left(|H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th}}{P_r} \sigma_2^2\right). \quad (11)$$

Consequently, the E2E outage probability, considering the D-COOK modulation scheme and the two Rx, two Tx configuration of the VLC link, is expressed in equation (12).

In the context of a conventional modulation scheme employed for the VLC link, and assuming that γ_2 represents the sole communication link between the relay and the destination, equation (12) can be modified for a typical THz-VLC scenario as in equation (13).

The BER for the source-relay THz link considering the QAM modulation scheme can be expressed as follows:

$$BER_{THz} = \frac{2}{\log_2 M} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}}\right) \operatorname{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{2(M-1)}} \gamma_1\right)$$

The BER for the relay-destination VLC link considering D-COOK modulation can be obtained through the unified error rate expression in [10] as,

$$BER_{VLCDC} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_2}{2}} + \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_3}{2}} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_2}{2}} \cdot \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_3}{2}} \right) \quad (14)$$

The E2E BER of the THz-VLC link, where the THz link uses QAM and the VLC link employs the proposed D-COOK modulation scheme, can be obtained through the expression of the unified error rate in [10] and can be expressed using equation (15).

$$BER_{E2E} = BER_{THz} + BER_{VLCDC} - 2 \cdot BER_{THz} \cdot BER_{VLCDC} \quad (15)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section assesses the proposed system's performance through simulations – it measures the BER, outage probability, and data rate. Table I details the simulation parameters. A 0.3 THz frequency was selected for its reduced absorption losses relative to higher THz frequencies [11]. The THz link distance was set to 30 meters, in accordance with typical UAV operating altitudes, while the indoor VLC link distance was 2 meters, reflecting the standard range between a light source and the receiver. Other parameters are derived from peer-reviewed sources.

In Fig. 3, the BER performance of three dual-hop communication systems—RF-VLC, FSO-VLC, and THz-VLC—is evaluated and compared. The first hop, connecting the source

to the relay, utilizes either RF, THz, or FSO utilizing BPSK modulation (represented by dotted lines with square markers) and 4-QAM modulation (represented by solid lines with circular markers). This first link covers a distance of 30 meters. The second hop, which uses VLC for transmission, employs conventional OOK modulation (dotted lines with square markers) and the proposed D-COOK modulation scheme (solid lines with circular markers) over a 5-meter link. The figure demonstrates that at lower SNR levels, RF-VLC and FSO-VLC systems outperform the THz-VLC system. This is largely due to the shorter wavelengths of THz signals, which are more prone to absorption by atmospheric gases and attenuation from obstacles, resulting in higher signal loss and performance degradation under low SNR conditions. However, as SNR increases, the THz-VLC system begins to outperform both FSO-VLC and RF-VLC. The disadvantages associated with THz communication, such as greater absorption and attenuation, become less significant at higher SNR levels. Additionally, the higher bandwidth and data rate potential of THz signals compared to RF and optical signals enable the THz-VLC system to capitalize on these advantages, resulting in superior BER performance as SNR improves. When comparing the performance of the

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
Number of bits	1e5	Distance [THz]	30 m
Frequency [THz]	0.3 THz	Antenna radius [THz]	0.1 m
Footprint radius	0.6 m	Distance [VLC]	5 m
Photo-diode Area	0.05	Source power, P_s	1 dB
Relay power, P_r	1 dB	θ	53.13°
ψ_c	75°	ψ	53.13°
Refractive index	1.5	Distance [FSO/RF]	30 m
α [FSO]	4.1	β [FSO]	1.4

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

systems using OOK and D-COOK, indicated by dotted lines with square markers and solid lines with circular markers respectively, it is observed that the proposed D-COOK modulation scheme exhibits slightly poorer performance than the BPSK/OOK configuration across all three communication paradigms. This outcome is expected, as D-COOK involves the transmission of a higher number of bits compared to OOK, leading to increased susceptibility to errors. Nonetheless, the performance gap between the two configurations narrows as SNR increases, indicating the robustness of D-COOK under high-SNR conditions. Additionally, in Fig. 4, it can be observed that the channel capacity of the 4-QAM/D-COOK is twice that of BPSK/OOK.

In Fig. 5, the outage probability of three hybrid communication systems—THz-VLC, RF-VLC, and FSO-VLC—is analyzed under different modulation configurations. For each system, similar to the BER simulations, two configurations are compared: one using 4-QAM modulation for the first hop with a link distance of 30m combined with the proposed D-COOK modulation for the second hop with a link distance of 3m, and another using BPSK for the first hop combined

$$P_{\text{out}_{PM}} = P\left(|H_{THz}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_s} \sigma_{SR}^2\right) + P\left(|H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_r} \sigma_2^2 \cap |H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_r} \sigma_2^2\right) - P\left(|H_{THz}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_s} \sigma_{SR}^2\right) \cdot P\left(|H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_r} \sigma_2^2 \cap |H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_r} \sigma_2^2\right). \quad (12)$$

$$P_{\text{out}} = P\left(|H_{THz}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_s} \sigma_{SR}^2\right) + P\left(|H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_r} \sigma_{RD}^2\right) - P\left(|H_{THz}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_s} \sigma_{SR}^2\right) \cdot P\left(|H_{VLC}|^2 < \frac{\gamma^{\text{th}}}{P_r} \sigma_{RD}^2\right). \quad (13)$$

Fig. 3. BER performance comparison for THz-VLC, RF-VLC, and FSO-VLC, using BPSK for the first hop and OOK for the second hop, as well as 4-QAM for the first hop and D-COOK for the second hop.

Fig. 4. The comparison of channel capacity for the proposed system using BPSK for the first hop and OOK for the second hop, as well as 4-QAM for the first hop and D-COOK for the second hop.

with conventional OOK for the second hop with same link distances, respectively.

The results demonstrate that, across all three communication systems, the 4-QAM/D-COOK configuration consistently outperforms the BPSK/OOK configuration in terms of outage probability, particularly at lower SNR values. This advantage can be attributed to the dual-channel configuration of the D-COOK modulation, as the outage occurs only if the

SNR of both channels in the relay-destination link falls below the threshold. This performance gain is more pronounced in the THz-VLC system, where the 4-QAM/D-COOK configuration shows a steep reduction in outage probability as the SNR increases. This is due to the high bandwidth and data rate potential of the THz link, which is effectively leveraged by the D-COOK modulation scheme in the VLC link.

In contrast, the RF-VLC and FSO-VLC systems exhibit more gradual improvements in outage probability with increasing SNR. The RF-VLC system, although less susceptible to atmospheric absorption than the THz system, demonstrates higher outage probabilities at lower SNRs due to the narrower bandwidth. Meanwhile, the FSO-VLC system shows a relatively balanced performance, with the 4-QAM/D-COOK configuration maintaining a consistent advantage over the BPSK/OOK configuration across the SNR range.

To further understand the effectiveness of the proposed D-COOK modulation scheme for THz-VLC link, in Fig. 6, the outage probability of the proposed system is analyzed by varying the relay-destination link distance while keeping the source-relay link constant.

The figure reveals that for a short relay-to-destination link distance of 2 meters, both configurations exhibit nearly identical outage probabilities. However, as the distance of the VLC link increases, the performance of the 4-QAM/D-COOK configuration surpasses that of the BPSK/OOK configuration, particularly at higher SNR values. This demonstrates the robustness of the D-COOK modulation scheme in maintaining lower outage probabilities over extended VLC link distances, compared to the conventional OOK scheme.

While the 4-QAM/D-COOK modulation configuration does not surpass the traditional BPSK/OOK in terms of BER performance under lower SNR conditions, it demonstrates significant potential in high-SNR environments. The slight degradation in BER is counterbalanced by the notable increase in channel capacity and outage probability, as seen in the comparative analysis. This trade-off between BER, capacity and outage probability suggests that D-COOK is particularly suited for scenarios where bandwidth efficiency and outage probability is prioritized over minimal error rates, especially in high-SNR applications due to the superior performance of THz-VLC systems at high SNRs.

Fig. 5. Outage probability performance comparison for THz-VLC, RF-VLC, and FSO-VLC. The comparison is made using BPSK for the first hop and OOK for the second hop, as well as 4-QAM for the first hop and D-COOK for the second hop.

Fig. 6. The comparison of outage probability for the proposed system using BPSK for the first hop and OOK for the second hop, as well as 4-QAM for the first hop and D-COOK for the second hop.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a novel Dual-Channel On-Off Keying modulation scheme within a UAV-assisted hybrid THz and VLC system. This system leverages the complementary strengths of THz and VLC technologies to enhance communication efficiency, particularly in environments demanding high data rates and low latency.

The proposed D-COOK modulation scheme, utilizing RGB LEDs for VLC, significantly increases data transmission rates by encoding two bits per symbol, thereby surpassing the performance of conventional OOK modulation. Simulation results have demonstrated that the THz-VLC system with 4-QAM/D-COOK modulation outperforms RF-VLC and FSO-VLC systems in terms of BER and outage probability, particularly under high SNR conditions. This advantage is largely due to the high directional gain and extensive bandwidth of the THz link, coupled with the innovative dual-channel approach in the VLC link.

Future work should focus on refining adaptive beam-steering techniques, enhancing power management, and developing robust encryption methods to mitigate issues like molecular absorption and pointing errors.

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